

ZAMONAVIY O‘ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGI, ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIGI VA TIL TA‘LIMINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI

mavzusidagi respublika
ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,**

Tilshunos olim **Abdullayev Jumanazar Xudoyberdiyevichning** 70 yilligiga
bag‘ishlangan

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THE NATIONAL AND CULTURAL SPECIFICITY OF ANTHROPOZOOMORPHISMS IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES I

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Annotation. *This article analyzes the national and cultural characteristics of anthropozoomorphisms in the Uzbek and English languages based on linguocultural and cognitive approaches. The study examines the mechanisms of expressing human character through animal imagery, their role in metaphorical and phraseological systems, and the similarities and differences across languages. In particular, using zoomorphic images such as the fox, bull, and pig, the reflection of national thinking and cultural stereotypes in linguistic units is demonstrated. Furthermore, the study substantiates the issues of adequate translation of anthropozoomorphic units, the challenges of selecting equivalent variants, and the importance of etymological explanations.*

Keywords: *anthropozoomorphism, linguoculturology, cognitive metaphor, phraseological unit, concept, national and cultural specificity, translation, equivalence, zoometaphor, semantic model*

In recent years, research conducted within the framework of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics has made it possible to study the complex relationships between language and thought, as well as language and culture, at a new level. In particular, in the fields of linguocognitology and linguoculturology, the study of metaphor, concepts, and their national and cultural foundations has become one of the most actual issues. From this perspective, a comparative analysis of anthropozoomorphisms in structurally different languages - specifically Uzbek and English - holds not only theoretical but also practical significance for linguistics.

Anthropozoomorphisms are linguistic units formed on the basis of describing a human through characteristics typical of the animal world, and they reflect the worldview, values, and cultural experience of a particular people. Such units occupy an

important place in the conceptual sphere of a language and demonstrate stereotypes and evaluative criteria formed in the national consciousness. Although expressing human character through animal imagery is a universal phenomenon inherent to human cognition, their interpretation and semantic load manifest in a culture-specific way in each society.

In Uzbek and English, as in many other languages, comparisons based on the animal world are widely used. From birth, humans are surrounded by reality, in which attention is often given to the similarities between human and animal behavior and character. The lifestyle of animals and their distinctive features are perceived through human cognition and are often intertwined with imagination. Representatives of one culture may emphasize certain traits of animals, while those of another culture highlight different aspects; this is often explained by the “mythological context.” The characteristics of animals as depicted in myths, legends, fairy tales, and epics become firmly embedded in the consciousness of a given culture, and particular traits come to be associated with specific animals as standard features, which are then verbalized in language. For example, in Uzbek culture, both domestic and wild animals such as *dogs, cats, horses, camels, donkeys, roosters, hens, sheep, rams, cows, calves, oxen, pigs, boars, wolves, lions, bears, monkeys, gazelles, deer, hares, and foxes* serve as the basis for similes. In English culture, animals such as the *cat, fox, mouse, cock, hen, dog, goose, wolf, donkey, frog, bear, pig, bull, horse, lion, eagle, pigeon, kite, raven, and parrot* also hold a specific place in figurative comparisons.

Demonstrating the language-specific features of anthropozoomorphisms in different languages in a way that corresponds to the original is of great importance for understanding and interpreting the national and cultural worldview inherent in a particular language. For example, in many languages, including the Uzbek linguistic worldview, a cunning and deceitful person is compared to a “fox.” There are numerous proverbs and sayings describing such a person, such as “*Tulki kabi tumshug‘idan ilindi*” or “*Ko‘zbo‘yamachi tulki bo‘ladi, xalq ichida kulgi bo‘ladi*”. In English culture, the fox also occupies a distinctive place. It simultaneously embodies the image of a cunning pest, a symbol of aristocratic traditions, and an animal adapted to urban life. The fox is associated with intelligence, agility, cleverness, and the ability to survive: sly as a fox, old fox. In English folklore, the figure of **Robin Hood** can be metaphorically associated with the fox, as this character fights against oppression not through open force, but through intelligence, cunning, and strategy, symbolizing the restoration of social justice. In this sense, Robin Hood embodies the metaphorical qualities of the *fox* in human form and represents a positive image in the collective imagination of the people. In both Uzbek and English, the evaluation of the fox as cunning or clever reflects the long-standing ontological perception embedded in the consciousness of these peoples: *tulki*

→ *tulkiday ayyor* = *ayyor odam*; *fox* → *sly as a fox* = *a sly person*. Therefore, in the process of translation, it is essential to be aware of the national and cultural nuances of a language in order to preserve its specific metaphorical meanings.

In scholarly literature, it has long been emphasized that among Turkic peoples, including Uzbeks, animals such as the wolf, bear, eagle, lion, snake, ox, sheep, goat, falcon, and hawk have been particularly revered [2,2007]. The study revealed that anthropozoomorphisms and fixed zoo-similes in Uzbek and English share common features; however, their figurative bases may differ. For example, in the fixed zoo-simile “*like a bull in a china shop*,” national characteristics specific to the English worldview are reflected, where strong but clumsy and tactless people are compared to a bull: “*He went on like a bull in a china shop*” (F. Marryat, Jacob Faithful).

A person belonging to the Uzbek nation, however, primarily associates this animal with qualities such as strength and endurance: *buqadek kuchli*, *buqadek baquvvat*, *buqadek sog‘lom*. For example: “*U buqadek baquvvat, keng yelkali yigit bo‘lib, og‘ir yuklarni bemalol ko‘tarardi*” (Oybek, Qutlug‘ qon). When translating such zoometaphors, it is not crucial whether the figurative basis (the bull) is replaced by another image; what matters most is that the original meaning is preserved and that the translated text remains adequate to the source.

In English, comparative phraseological units such as *as dirty as a pig* and *as greedy as a pig* do not pose significant difficulty in finding their Uzbek equivalents. When human behavior is compared to the image of a pig, one of the shared features of this anthropozoomorphism in both languages is its use to express derogation (dirty, filthy) and insult (scoundrel, animal). However, in Spanish culture, another comparative phraseological expression associated with the pig – *to sweat like a pig* – does not occur in Uzbek. In translating or providing equivalents for such fixed zoo-similes, it becomes necessary to refer to etymology. This expression is used to describe a person who is sweating heavily due to heat or discomfort. Despite this expression, pigs actually hardly sweat. In this expression, the word “pig” actually derives from the term pig iron (cast iron). According to data from McGill University, this phrase originates from the process of smelting iron. In this process, molten iron is poured into sand molds, and as it cools and solidifies, it forms shapes resembling a sow and her piglets. For this reason, it is called pig iron. As the iron cools, the surrounding air reaches the dew point, and droplets of moisture appear on the surface of the pig iron. Thus, the expression “*to sweat like a pig*” originally referred to the stage at which the iron has cooled enough to be handled safely. When an English speaker uses the zoomorphic expression to sweat like a pig to describe heavy sweating, it may be unclear to an Uzbek speaker; in this case, the Uzbek equivalent *terlab-pishib ketmoq* would be appropriate. However, when expressions such as *as dirty as a pig* are used, the implicit meaning can be easily understood, since Uzbek

has equivalent expressions like *cho‘chqadek kir/iflos*, which do not create difficulties in translation. Thus, in the linguistic worldview, the general features of a particular zoomorphism do not create significant difficulties in the process of translation; rather, it is the language-specific metaphors and expressions that require the translator’s skill and knowledge to find appropriate equivalents. The relatively limited number of comparative phraseological units (CPUs) with the lexeme “pig” in Uzbek, compared to English, may be explained by the fact that not all characteristics associated with this animal have been assimilated into Uzbek national culture. This type of livestock is not widespread in Uzbekistan and is not commonly raised in Uzbek households like cows, sheep, or horses. Therefore, its general features – such as dirtiness, fatness, or eating messily – are familiar to Uzbeks, whereas aspects like sweating are not commonly associated with it. The variability of expressions also confirms that the characteristics of this animal are more deeply integrated into English culture: to sweat like a pig. For example: “*I was sweating like a pig, my shirt sticking to my back and my hands so damp I could hardly keep my grip*” (S. King, *The Dead Zone*). In translating the anthropozoomorphism sweating like a pig, it is possible to use calque or culturally adapted Uzbek equivalents such as *cho‘chqaday terga botmoq*, *terlab-pishib ketmoq*, or *qora terga botib*. For instance: “*U qora terga botib, nafasi qisilib, biroz to‘xtab olishga majbur bo‘ldi.*” (A. Qodiriy, *O‘tgan kunlar*).

Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that although anthropozoomorphisms in Uzbek and English share a common cognitive foundation, their national and cultural interpretations and figurative bases differ significantly. In both languages, the evaluation of human character through animal imagery is a universal phenomenon, serving as an expression of linguistic and cultural stereotypes. However, the semantic load assigned to particular animals, their positive or negative evaluation, and their scope of use are shaped by national thinking and historical experience. In the process of translation, it is essential to take these national and cultural features into account, to select appropriate phraseological equivalents, and, when necessary, to employ descriptive translation. Anthropozoomorphisms are thus recognized as important linguocultural units that reveal the intrinsic connection between language and culture.

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O‘ZBEK TILIDAGI HOLAT FE’LLARIGA ASOS BO‘LUVCHI QARDOSH BO‘LMAGAN TILLARDAGI NAZARIY MUNOSABATLAR

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada o‘zbek tilidagi holat fe’llarining lingvistik xususiyatlari hamda ularning qardosh bo‘lmagan tillardagi nazariy talqinlari tahlil qilinadi. Holat fe’llari predmet yoki shaxsning ichki va tashqi holatini ifodalovchi grammatik birliklar sifatida til tizimida muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Tadqiqotda o‘zbek tilidagi holat fe’llarining semantik va grammatik jihatlari ingliz, rus va boshqa qardosh bo‘lmagan tillardagi mos kategoriyalar bilan qiyosiy o‘rganiladi. Shuningdek, ularning ifodalanish usullari, zamon va aspekt bilan bog‘liqligi, hamda tipologik farqlari yoritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: holat fe’llari, o‘zbek tili, qiyosiy tilshunoslik, semantika, grammatika, aspekt, tipologiya, qardosh bo‘lmagan tillar, lingvistik tahlil.

Abstract. This article analyzes the linguistic features of state verbs in the Uzbek language and their theoretical interpretations in non-relative languages. State verbs occupy an important place in the language system as grammatical units expressing the internal and external state of an object or person. The study studies the semantic and grammatical aspects of state verbs in the Uzbek language in comparison with the corresponding categories in English, Russian and other non-relative languages. It also highlights their methods of expression, their relationship with tense and aspect, and their typological differences.

Keywords: state verbs, Uzbek language, comparative linguistics, semantics, grammar, aspect, typology, non-relative languages, linguistic analysis.